

Experienced EFL Teachers' Resilience and the Role of Social-Emotional Competence

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Abstract: Teacher resilience is a complex process that incorporates various factors and competences, among which social-emotional competence (SEC) is the leading one. Hence, this study investigates the resilience of EFL teachers, with a focus on the role of SEC in this process. Four experienced English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers participated in the study. Data were collected through three interview methods (i.e., narrative, critical incident, and reinterviews) by converting teachers' remarks into narratives with a focus on temporal sequentiality and causality. Findings indicated that teachers experienced various challenges in complex ways, resulting in changes in their professional performance. Regarding the dimensions of teacher resilience processes, the findings showed that despite strong connections between personal resources and strategies, as well as between contextual resources and strategies, moderate-level connections existed between personal resources and contextual resources. Additionally, weaker connections were found between outcomes and other dimensions, particularly between strategies and outcomes. Lastly, the findings pointed to the critical role of the SEC in all dimensions of the teacher resilience process.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Öğretmen dayanıklılığı
Sosyal-duygusal yeterlilik
Öğretmen hikayeleri
Kritik olaylar
Deneyimli İngilizce öğretmenleri

Deneyimli İngilizce Öğretmenlerinin Mesleki Dayanıklılıkları ve Sosyal-Duygusal Yeterliliğin Etkisi

Özet: Öğretmen dayanıklılığı, çeşitli faktörler ve yeterlilikleri içeren karmaşık bir süreç olup, bu süreçte sosyal-duygusal yeterlilik öne çıkan bir unsur olarak karşımıza çıkmaktadır. Bu bağlamda, bu çalışma, İngilizce'nin yabancı dil olarak öğretildiği bağlamda görev yapan öğretmenlerin dayanıklılık süreçlerini incelemekte ve bu süreçte sosyal-duygusal yeterliliğin rolünü merkeze almaktadır. Çalışmaya, deneyimli dört İngilizce öğretmeni katılmıştır. Veriler, üç farklı görüşme yöntemi (anlatısal, kritik olay ve yeniden görüşme) aracılığıyla toplanmıştır; öğretmenlerin ifadeleri, zamansal sıralılık ve nedensellik odaklı anlatılara dönüştürülmüştür. Bulgular, öğretmenlerin mesleki performanslarında değişimlere yol açan çeşitli zorlukları karmaşık biçimlerde deneyimlediklerini ortaya koymuştur. Öğretmen dayanıklılığı süreçlerinin boyutlarına ilişkin olarak, kişisel kaynaklar ile stratejiler arasında ve bağlamsal kaynaklar ile stratejiler arasında güçlü bağlantılar bulunurken, kişisel kaynaklar ile bağlamsal kaynaklar arasında orta düzeyde bir ilişki tespit edilmiştir. Ayrıca, sonuçlar ile diğer boyutlar (özellikle stratejiler ve sonuçlar) arasında daha zayıf bağlantılar olduğu görülmüştür. Son olarak, bulgular, sosyal-duygusal yeterliliğin öğretmen dayanıklılığı sürecinin tüm boyutlarında kritik bir rol oynadığına işaret etmektedir.

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1. Introduction

Although there are currently a myriad of highly advanced materials and other technological innovations aimed at improving the quality of language teaching, language teachers still play the most critical role in actualizing teaching and learning. Given that “an education system is only as good as its teachers” (UNESCO, 2015, p. 3), teacher quality emerges as a critical issue. In English language teaching (ELT), teacher quality is often associated with effective teaching and students' success (Arikan, 2006; Çelik *et al.*, 2013). However, teacher quality and effective language teaching depend on multiple dimensions, including various forms of teacher support, social and emotional aspects. This is mainly because teaching is not merely a matter of instruction; instead, it is a complex, demanding, and challenging profession that requires continuous development, planning, and organization. It also entails coping with various challenges and adversities stemming from administrators, colleagues, students, parents, or other factors (Boldrini *et al.*, 2019; Doney, 2013). In such cases, those who fail to overcome these difficulties tend to face emotional predicaments, including demotivation, stress, anxiety, apprehension, and boredom, as well as burnout, dissatisfaction, and professional disengagement (Wang *et al.*, 2024; Xie, 2021), ultimately leading to teacher attrition. With all these factors in mind, teacher resilience emerges as a critical factor affecting professional development (Mansfield *et al.*, 2016; Gu & Day, 2013), teacher engagement (Beltman *et al.*, 2011), and effective teaching (Gu & Day, 2007). In such a case, it can be said that the quality of teaching also depends on teachers' resilience.

1.1. Teacher Resilience

The concept of resilience first emerged from psychiatry and developmental psychology, driven by the popularity of research on children's specific characteristics that enable them to adapt successfully and thrive despite significant adversity (Gu & Day, 2013). Therefore, resilience was initially associated with adapting to and growing through adversity. However, other studies have indicated that resilience is not a single human trait but a multifaceted construct arising from a dynamic connection between risk and protective variables (Benard, 2004). Over the last three decades, the resilient qualities of teachers have emerged as a field of research and gained greater currency. In line with this, the literature provides a myriad of theoretical or empirical conceptualizations of teacher resilience. Despite their value and contributions, the wide range of definitions surrounding this term leads to uncertainty about its nature. Given the majority of definitions, teacher resilience is often associated with maintaining a commitment to teaching (Brunetti, 2006), overcoming personal vulnerability and environmental stressors (Oswald *et al.*, 2003), and recovering strengths or spirit (Sammons *et al.*, 2007) despite challenges and impediments. However, this study adopts a system-focused perspective, considering Beltman's (2020, p. 19) caveats that teacher resilience encompasses “individual characteristics, strategies, or processes” alongside “multiple systems and contexts.” Accordingly, in this study, teacher resilience refers to

the capacity of an individual to navigate through challenges and harness personal and contextual resources, as well as the process through which the characteristics of individual teachers and their personal and professional contexts interact over time, resulting in the outcome of a teacher who experiences professional commitment, growth, and well-being (Beltman, 2020, p. 21).

In line with Beltman's (2021) definition, teacher resilience is often understood not merely as a singular capacity but rather as a combination of capacity, process, and outcome (Mansfield *et al.*, 2016). This conceptualization enables researchers to view resilience as a dynamic and nonlinear construct, allowing for a detailed exploration of the interplay between its

components (see Figure 1). In this model, personal resources serve as an internal foundation for coping with challenges, while contextual resources provide external support. Strategies function as the mechanism through which individuals effectively utilize these resources. Given the nonlinear nature of this model, the interaction between resources and strategies evolves, influencing resilience outcomes (Beltmann, 2021). These outcomes, in turn, further enhance both personal and contextual resources, fostering sustained development. Mansfield et al.'s (2012) four-dimensional framework of teacher resilience also shows that teacher resilience is “a complex, dynamic and multi-dimensional” construct encompassing interconnected professional, emotional, motivational, and social dimensions, which may overlap and vary in intensity depending on the context (p. 364).

Figure 1. Dimensions of the teacher resilience process. Authors' own design. Adapted from Beltman (2020, p. 21)

In the field of ELT, previous studies on resilience revealed that teachers develop resilience by instilling a sense of purpose, viewing challenges as learning opportunities, leveraging relationships within their school communities, and navigating the complex interplay of internal and external factors that influence outcomes (Drew & Sosnowski, 2019), associated resilience with reflective teaching (Shirazizadeh et al., 2019), displayed survival, defensive and healthy tactics to remain resilient (Duan et al., 2023). Previous studies also showed that there is a positive correlation between EFL teachers' resilience and emotional regulation (Li & Lv, 2022); the interpersonal relationship is a necessary resource condition for teacher resilience development and plays an important role in teachers' social enjoyment (Zhang, 2023), intrinsic (e.g., emotion regulation, high self-confidence etc.) and extrinsic (e.g., positive interactions, close relationships etc.) factors played contributing role in their work engagement along with social and emotional factors play a critical role in EFL teachers' resilience (Xie, 2021).

1.2. Social-Emotional Competence in Teacher Resilience

Various models of teacher resilience identify emotional and social factors as critical components (e.g., Greenfield, 2015; Mansfield et al., 2012). Similarly, the SEC in Mansfield et al.'s (2016) model of resilience holds a critical position. The social part of competence

encompasses building and understanding relationships, particularly in the school environment, collaborative working, effective communication, building and enhancing support networks, and setting boundaries. The emotional aspect involves optimistic thinking, managing emotions, cultivating positive emotions, and developing emotional awareness. Therefore, the SEC lays a foundation for personal sources and directly influences the interplay between personal resources, contextual sources, strategies, and outcomes. Similarly, the literature on SEC also defines and construes it as a complex phenomenon, encompassing self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationships skills, and responsible decision-making (CASEL, 2025; Tom, 2012).

Figure 2. Dimensions of SEC. Authors' own design. Adapted from CASEL (2025) and Tom (2012, p. 47)

Previous studies have presented empirical results that underscore the criticality of SEC in teacher resilience. Knight's study (2007) asserts that teachers' sense of efficacy (SEC) is critical in building, maintaining, and improving resilience. Similarly, Ee and Chang (2010) revealed that SEC is among the key factors in manifesting resilience. Jennings and Greenberg (2009) noted that teachers' well-being decreases when they lack social-emotional competence (SEC), resulting in a negative classroom atmosphere. In the opposite cases, however, teachers' social-emotional competence enables them to manage and overcome students' demands, build rapport with students, and ultimately create a positive classroom atmosphere

that supports learning. Hong's (2012) study revealed that the teaching profession entails active response, negotiation, and interpretation of the dynamics in the classroom and school context; thus, teachers who manage to establish boundaries between themselves and the other stakeholders in this context while regulating social relations are less likely to experience burnout.

Previous studies on teachers' social and emotional competence mainly focus on implementing learning programs for pre-service teachers. However, more research and additional in-service development programs are needed "To support fresh graduates in their transition to the workforce" through "programs that offer tangible benefits and cultivate valuable experiential learning opportunities (Sitepu *et al.*, 2024, p. 281). Given that the teaching profession has social and emotional demands, which involve constant interaction with students, colleagues, and administrators, and the resulting emotional outcomes, SEC is a crucial component of teachers' resilience. However, as Collie and Perry (2019) caution, regarding SEC as a static trait or ability could be misleading simply because individuals' social and psychological needs interact continuously with their professional motivations, behaviors, and satisfaction. Therefore, although previous research has revealed that SEC plays a critical role in teachers' resilience and provides valuable insights into teacher resilience, this area remains under-researched due to the lack of studies directly focusing on SEC (Collie & Perry, 2019; Jennings & Greenberg, 2009).

1.3. Teacher Stories and Critical Incidents

Using teachers' stories has gained currency not only in teacher education but also in teacher education programs. These stories encapsulate valuable, both positive and negative, firsthand experiences and are thus considered significant teaching and learning tools for teacher candidates, other teachers, teacher trainers, and administrators (Connelly & Clandinin, 1990; Scherff, 2008). Due to their values, the terms "narrative" and "story" are theoretically defined in various and sometimes inconsistent ways. This problem stems from the myriad of definitions of those terms. Despite the various ways to define what a story is, in this study, this word is theoretically defined following Scholes' (1982, p. 59) remarks that a story is the telling or recounting of a sequence of events revolving around "a situation involving some predicament, conflict, or struggle" and a protagonist who actively engages in this situation. From this standpoint, the temporal sequentiality based on cause and effect in stories makes them a means for better understanding the "complexity, specificity, and interconnectedness of the phenomenon in question," being an alternative to quantitative approaches, in which teaching is "decomposed into discrete variables and indicators of effectiveness" (Carter, 1993, p. 5). Lyons and LaBoskey (2002) underline the value of teacher stories in educational research as follows:

Intentional, reflective human actions, socially and contextually situated, in which teachers, with their students, other colleagues, or researchers, interrogate their teaching practices to construct the meaning and interpretation of some compelling or puzzling aspect of teaching and learning through the production of narratives that lead to understanding, changed practices, and new hypotheses (p. 21)

This perspective is critical because teachers' professional development is a lifelong and ongoing process. Thus, it is a life history within which "the past, the present, and the future are always in mind" (Connelly & Clandinin, 1994, p. 147). Therefore, when these stories are recorded, they can be revisited, providing valuable opportunities for reflection, learning from their values, beliefs, professional environment, teaching practices, and, thus, a better

understanding of their experiences (Connelly & Clandinin, 1990; Scherff, 2008). Additionally, studying teachers' stories provides a frame of reference for understanding the professional lives of other teachers while revealing the uniqueness of each teacher's life (Scherff, 2008).

Just as stories involve moments that pave the way for significant results, teacher stories are rich in such moments. Those significant moments are defined as critical incidents that can serve as anchor points within broader narratives. They highlight moments when participants faced decisions, changes, or realizations contributing to their evolving teaching identities. While teachers narrate their professional stories about a particular topic or event, they often refer to particular events or happenings. At this juncture, however, it must be underlined that "a student's accidentally dropping their class text on the floor during a lesson is not a critical incident" (Nejadghanbar, 2021, p. 3). What makes such moments critical is that there must be "a departure from normal and predictable classroom events and ones that prompt deep processing of the event through critical reflection" (Nejadghanbar, 2021, p. 3). Therefore, critical incidents are transformative moments that alter teachers' mindsets and practices (Tripp, 2012). In line with this, these incidents influence how teachers perceive their present situation mainly because they interact with "their identity, beliefs, values, and sense of competence" (Lasky, 2005, p. 901). Therefore, the identification and analysis of critical incidents entail descriptions, explanations, and evaluations of their contributions and transformative effects (Derakhshan & Nazari, 2023). With all these factors in mind, this study defines critical incidents as events that significantly influence teachers' resilience. Hence, given the pressing need for studies on EFL teachers' resilience, this study aims to investigate the challenges they encounter, factors contributing to resilience, and the role of SEC based on critical incidents, and seek answers to the research questions below:

1. What challenges appear from teachers' critical incidents? What personal resources, contextual resources, and strategies do they use? What are the outcomes?
2. What is the role of the SEC in these critical incidents about teacher resilience?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

The qualitative research design was deemed the best course of action as this way of inquiry allows researchers to investigate a phenomenon through analyzing and interpreting nonnumerical data (e.g., narrative or visual, etc.) collected from contexts that are not controlled or manipulated to gain insights into a particular phenomenon of interest (Gay et al., 2012).

2.2. Participants and Contexts

In line with the study's aim, a purposive sampling method was employed, following an initial set of criteria (Cohen et al., 2018). These criteria were having at least ten years of teaching experience without any intervals and working at a state school since the beginning of their teaching career. Among twenty-one teachers meeting these criteria, four teachers (Amber, Cherry, Nina, and Pearl, all pseudonyms) volunteered to participate in the study. Three participants received their BA diplomas from the Department of English Language and Teaching, and the other graduated from the Department of English Language and Literature with a certificate in English language teaching (see Table 1 for details about the participants). Each participant worked at different state schools in different parts of Türkiye.

Table 1.
Participants' Demographics

Descriptors	Amber	Cherry	Nina	Pearl
Age	37	40	43	44
Gender	All participants were female English language teachers.			
Undergraduate education	English Language & Literature		ELT	
Postgraduate education	No	M.A. in ELT	M.A. in Curriculum Development	No
Years of teaching experience	14	17	20	22
School type	All participants worked at different state schools throughout their teaching careers.			
School location	South-eastern Anatolia	Black Sea	Central Anatolia	Southern Anatolia

2.3. Data Collection Procedure and Analysis

Data were collected by employing three different interview methods. First, narrative interview sessions were conducted individually with each participant. This type of interviewing is found to be efficient in collecting individuals' particular experiences as storied expressions (Anderson & Kirkpatrick, 2016), which helps gain deeper insight into the phenomenon in question. Accordingly, these interview sessions focused on understanding the experiences connected to their resilience. During the narrative interviewing sessions, the researcher gave participants more leeway to narrate their stories and refrained from imposing any specific agenda. However, follow-up questions were also asked for clarification, specification, and exemplification (Gemignani, 2014). The second-round interviews were conducted using the critical incident technique to focus on participants' particular experiences that characterized their resilience (Simmons, 2017). During these sessions, the researcher posed additional questions to the participants, such as how, why, where, and when, to further detail the narratives. Lastly, a reinterview session was conducted to verify the points mentioned in the first two sessions and refine the findings (Lavrakas, 2008).

Following Josselson's (2006) caveat that analyzing narrative data is "always interpretive" (p. 4), the narrative smoothing method was employed to adjust the focus in a way that mediates readers' understanding. Methodologically, as Gracia (2012) outlines, this process is completed in five steps (i.e., focus, omission, addition, appropriation, and transposition). While focus refers to presenting the critical elements of a story, omission involves excluding irrelevant elements; addition enriches stories by including details or elements to provide a comprehensive understanding; and transposition uses a theme in a different context to represent meaning that may not have been captured previously. Researchers imbue the narrative with personal resonance during appropriation, reinterpreting and reshaping it while "making it their own" (p. 225). After finalizing critical incidents, member checking was followed. Each participant read their own critical incidents, and some minor revisions were made. Lastly, each critical incident was analyzed using Atlas.ti qualitative analysis software regarding challenges, personal resources, contextual resources, strategies, outcomes, and the dimensions of SEC. In this way, findings convey how critical incidents unfolded in each teacher's case, allowing readers to experience those critical incidents firsthand (Chase, 2003). Additionally, peer debriefing was employed to ensure trustworthiness (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

3. Findings

3.1. Challenges of Resilience

This study presents the findings derived from an analysis of 12 critical incidents that emerged from the interview sessions with the participants. It is important to note that more than 12 (critical) incidents were initially identified, particularly during the first interviews. However, applying the exclusion criteria systematically reduced the number of critical incidents, and only those related to teacher resilience were included. First, the challenges of resilience were analyzed in the four cases. Table 2 presents those challenges that emerged from participants' critical incidents.

Table 2.

Challenges across Cases (Incident-based)

Pseudonyms	Challenges of Teacher Resilience		
	Critical Incident 1	Critical Incident 2	Critical Incident 3
Amber	Student-related Personal	Administrative Collegial Parental	Student-related Personal Collegial
Nina	Administrative Parental Student-related	Administrative Personal	Personal Student-related
Cherry	Collegial	Personal Student-related	Collegial Student-related
Pearl	Administrative Collegial	Collegial	Personal Student-related

As shown in Table 2, participants experienced a range of challenges, including student-related ($n = 7$), personal ($n = 6$), collegial ($n = 6$), administrative ($n = 4$), and parental ($n = 2$) issues. Figure 3 also presents further details about resilience challenges across cases. Accordingly, findings showed that the participants experienced different types of challenges and sometimes did not experience particular types of challenges. Accordingly, Amber experienced various challenges, whereas Nina did not encounter any challenges resulting from collegial issues or conflicts. Similarly, Pearl experienced four types of challenges apart from parental ones. Cherry's case portrayed a different picture and showed that she did not experience challenges from administrative problems and conflicts with students' parents.

In addition to these overall results, the analysis of the critical incidents also showed that these challenges occurred in intertwined and complex ways. The following excerpt from the first critical incident in Amber's case vividly exemplifies this:

A variant of Arabic was the region's dominant language; thus, most children only learned Turkish at school. Additionally, families did not attach much importance to education, particularly learning English, due to the region's socioeconomic structure... I had difficulty communicating with my students, and classes did not progress as planned due to the language barrier. Furthermore, students' frequent absences made things even more complicated. Many students had to help their families with agricultural work and were unable to attend school for weeks. (Excerpt from Amber's first critical incident)

Although Amber's communication problems with her students and their negative attitudes toward learning English appeared to be a challenge to her resilience, these issues were a direct result of the sociocultural and socioeconomic realities of the region. These realities emerged as challenges to her resilience in the school environment and classroom, combined with the lack of training to teach under such circumstances during her teacher education.

Figure 3. Challenges across cases

Cherry's case also provides an excellent example showing the intertwined and complex nature of resilience challenges. The challenges Cherry faced in the second critical incident were a direct result of the first incident. In the first critical incident, Cherry had to work with colleagues who were highly experienced and used old-fashioned teaching methods, focusing solely on grammar, reading, and vocabulary. Cherry thought this method prevented students from truly learning English and wanted them to learn the language by experiencing and using it. However, this view was not well received by the other teachers. The discussions in the meetings were becoming increasingly tense. However, Cherry continued to defend her understanding of teaching despite sometimes feeling lonely and excluded. As she continued to do her job in her own way, Cherry gradually became increasingly isolated. Her colleagues either did not speak to her at all or only exchanged a few words when necessary, and in meetings, they openly opposed her. Eventually, Cherry decided to change her school due to the reasons given below:

So, I learned that it wasn't possible to stay in that school and struggle to change them [her colleagues]. I thought it was the only way to continue doing my job because I feared that one day, after spending enough years with such teachers, I would become like them. (Excerpt from Cherry's first critical incident)

She encountered highly demanding students at her new school, making Cherry afraid of being judged incompetent:

I was assigned to a science high school where students were enthusiastic about learning English. It was the best decision in my teaching career. However, working with such curious, inquisitive, and ambitious

students made me feel uneasy because I constantly feared that I was not competent enough. First, my workload increased because I was expected to prepare extra materials, use alternative assessment methods, and organize extra-curricular activities. (Excerpt from Cherry's second critical incident)

The analysis of the critical incidents also showed that, in some cases, teachers face unexpected challenges. For instance, Amber suddenly found herself in the middle of a grilling without any prior warning or preparation, as the principal had brought the parent to the teachers' lounge. Amber explains how she felt as follows:

I did not know what to say. However, I felt terrible because I had never considered how I would react in such a situation or had never encountered a similar one. I was scared and stressed. (Excerpt from Amber's second critical incident)

The biggest problem for Amber was that she was caught unprepared and dragged into a quarrel. She says, "If the principal had informed me in advance, we could have had this conversation on much healthier grounds." Similarly, Nina found herself in a predicament when she learned she had been temporarily assigned to another school due to a sudden teacher shortage. Pearl also found herself in a difficult situation when one of her students suddenly jumped out of the window during class time.

3.2. Dimensions of Resilience

The detailed analysis of the critical incidents also revealed further insights into the dimensions of resilience (see Table 3). As for personal resources, sense of vocation ($f = 9$) and sense of purpose ($f = 6$) appeared in each participant's case and thus emerged as the most frequently used personal resources. In contrast, value as a personal resource only appeared in a single critical incident. Regarding contextual factors, the findings revealed that relationships with students ($f = 11$) were the most frequently used resource and appeared in each participant's case. In contrast, social networks ($f = 1$) emerged as the least frequently used contextual resource. As for the strategies, emotional regulation ($f = 6$), problem-solving ($f = 5$), and communication ($f = 5$) were the most frequently used strategies, whereas goal setting ($f = 1$) was the least used strategy. Lastly, commitment ($f = 8$) and well-being ($f = 6$) were the most frequently reported outcomes in teachers' critical incidents.

When dimensions of the teacher resilience process were analyzed across cases, distinct patterns with varying reliance on contextual, personal, and strategic resources emerged (see Figure 4). Findings showed that Amber's resilience heavily relied on contextual resources ($f = 14$) and strategies ($f = 14$), suggesting that her resilience is strongly mediated by strategies primarily based on relationships with her students. The following quote vividly exemplifies how she actively maintains relationships with her students as her contextual resources:

I began learning basic Arabic expressions to communicate more effectively with my students. Unexpectedly, they helped me with great enthusiasm during this process. As a teacher, learning from her students while teaching was a new and exciting experience for me. (Excerpt from Amber's first critical incident)

In contrast to Amber, Cherry's and Pearl's cases showed a balanced combination of strategies ($f=5$ for each), outcomes ($f = 5$ for each), and personal resources ($f = 4$ for Cherry and $f = 3$ for Pearl), and minimal engagement with the contextual resources ($f = 1$ for Cherry and $f = 2$ for Pearl), underlining self-reliant nature of their resilience (see Figure 4). In both cases,

the scarcity of contextual resources stemmed from the lack of collegial support and conflicts with her colleagues, as exemplified below:

As I continued to do my job in my own way, I gradually became increasingly isolated. My colleagues either did not speak to me at all or only exchanged a few words when necessary, and in meetings, they openly opposed me. (Excerpt from Cherry's first critical incident)

At the end of my eight-month teaching career, I began considering quitting due to the heavy workload, the principal's behavior, and the lack of guidance from my colleagues. (Excerpt from Pearl's first critical incident)

Table 3.

Dimensions of Teacher Resilience Process (frequencies)

Personal Resources (21) *	Contextual Resources (22)	Strategies ** (34)	Outcomes (31) **
		Emotional regulation (6)	
	Relationship with students (11)	Communication (5)	Strategies as outcome (10)
Sense of vocation (9)		Problem-solving (5)	
Sense of purpose (6)	Colleagues (5)	Persistence (4)	Commitment (8)
Courage (3)	Family support (3)	Self-reflection (3)	Well-being (6)
Motivation (2)	School leaders (2)	Setting boundaries (3)	Responsibility (4)
Value (1)	Social networks (1)	Failed strategies (3)	Job satisfaction (3)
		Work-life balance (2)	
		Help-seeking (2)	
		Goal setting (1)	

* SEC, as a personal resource, was excluded from this data analysis step to avoid unnecessary repetitions. ** For "failed strategies" and "strategies as outcome," please see Figure 5.

Lastly, Nina's case presented a balanced distribution in almost all dimensions of the teacher resilience process, suggesting an integrated and more flexible approach to resilience. Colleagues, students, school leaders, and family support serve as contextual resources, complementing her help-seeking and communication strategies and highlighting her flexibility when she encounters challenges. The following quotes vividly illustrate this finding:

After the quarrel with the principal, I called my husband, and together, we went to the provincial and national education directorates to seek help with this problem. Eventually, the authorities helped me and solved the issue, and my reassignment was canceled. (Excerpt from Nina's second critical incident)

In addition, findings indicated critical commonalities and differences compared to Mansfield *et al.*'s (2016) model of the teacher resilience process. First, as shown in Figure 5, strong connections were found between contextual resources and strategies ($f = 9$) and personal resources and strategies ($f = 8$). In contrast, moderate-level connections were found between personal resources and contextual resources ($f = 4$) and between personal resources and outcomes ($f = 4$), while weak connections were found between contextual resources and outcomes ($f = 1$). Additionally, in some cases, contextual resources were linked to strategies through personal resources ($f = 4$) and outcomes ($f = 1$), while strategies were linked to outcomes through personal resources ($f = 3$). The second critical incident from Nina's case exemplifies the mediator role of personal resources:

... the boy suddenly burst into tears and left the classroom in a hurry. I couldn't understand why he acted like this. During break time, I spoke with a female student from the same class, and she informed me that the boy had no parents and was living in an orphanage. Words are not enough to describe how shame and guilt washed over me like a tidal wave. I should have understood my students' worlds

and considered their sensitivities. Therefore, first, I contacted the school's counseling department and learned more about my students' sensitivities. (Excerpt from Nina's third critical incident)

Figure 4. Dimensions of teacher resilience across cases

Accordingly, when Nina encountered a problem with a student during class due to the student's mistake and negative attitude, she used some students as contextual resources to gain more information about the issue. After learning the reasons behind the problem, Nina consulted with the school's counseling department, utilizing her sense of vocation as a personal resource. Finally, she engaged in self-reflection on her behaviors and decided to communicate directly with the student to resolve the problem. Second, this analysis was iterated, incorporating challenges, failed strategies, and strategies that emerged as outcomes to gain deeper insights (see Figure 5). Findings indicated strong connections between challenges and contextual sources ($f = 7$), moderate-level connections between challenges and strategies ($f = 5$), and no direct connection between challenges and outcomes. With this in mind, the leftmost positioning of challenges in Figure 5 indicates their predominant role as a point of departure in participants' critical incidents. High co-occurrences with contextual resources and strategies, along with the absence of a direct connection with outcomes, underpin the notion that challenges serve as initiating events rather than endpoints. The following quotes from the beginning parts of the participants' critical incidents vividly illustrate this:

Over time, I began to experience some disappointments with both her colleagues and her students. (Excerpt from Amber's third critical incident)

My students were initially prejudiced against foreign languages because they thought they would not need to learn English. Therefore, Nina made a concerted effort to make her classes as enjoyable as possible and frequently emphasized the importance of learning English to her students. (Excerpt from Nina's third critical incident)

I started working at her new school, which was notorious for its bad-tempered and stubborn English teachers. (Excerpt from Cherry's first critical incident)

The school's principal was a stern woman in her mid-forties with a background in fine arts. She had made it a habit to summon me to her office for trivial reasons. (Excerpt from Pearl's first critical incident)

Findings also showed failed strategies and strategies that emerged as outcomes from teachers' critical incidents. Although failed strategies had a low frequency ($f = 3$), their existence in critical incidents suggested that teachers developed strategies using their personal and contextual resources; however, these strategies might not have been effective in overcoming the challenges. This finding suggests that failure is also a part of the resilience process.

Figure 5. The relationship between challenges and resilience

Lastly, in particular, certain critical incidents led to the emergence of specific strategies. For instance, after a conflict with a student's parent due to the principal's carelessness, Amber distanced herself from the principal and thought administrators only cared about themselves. In the cases of other participants, similar strategies emerged as outcomes. When Cherry went to court as a witness due to the conflict between her colleague and a student's parents, she testified against her colleague because she thought her colleague was wrong. However, the price of telling the truth was high for Cherry because her colleague ended their friendship, and some other teachers in the school started to act coldly towards Cherry. This incident led her to set boundaries between herself and her colleagues:

I understood the necessity of setting more precise emotional and professional boundaries to avoid undue pressure from colleagues in ethical dilemmas. (Excerpt from Cherry's third critical incident)

As can be seen in these examples, teachers also developed strategies in response to the challenges they faced and implemented them. This suggests that teacher resilience can also cultivate its own tools for future experiences.

3.3. SEC in the Resilience Process

Regarding the second research question, each critical incident was analyzed to gain deeper insights into the role of the SEC in the resilience process. Accordingly, code co-occurrences in the dimensions of teacher resilience (i.e., personal resources, contextual resources, strategies, and outcomes) and the dimensions of SEC (i.e., self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationships skills, and responsible decision-making) were compared and contrasted. As shown in Table 4, the findings indicate the critical role of the SEC in fostering teacher resilience across all dimensions in various ways. Accordingly, the strongest connection was found between the resilience strategies that teachers used and SEC ($f = 32$), which was primarily driven by self-management ($f = 14$), particularly regulating emotions and behaviors, with additional contributions from self-awareness ($f = 7$), social awareness (f

= 5), and responsible decision-making (f = 4). The second strongest connection was found between personal resources and SEC (f = 20), in which self-management (f = 8) plays a critical role, with additional contributions from social awareness (f = 4), responsible decision-making (f = 4), and self-awareness (f = 3). However, a moderate correlation was found between contextual resources and SEC (f = 15) compared to strategies and personal resources. The findings indicated a relatively balanced distribution, with self-management (f = 5) and social awareness (f = 4) as the primary contributors and smaller contributions from the other dimensions. Lastly, the findings indicated the weakest connection between SEC and outcomes (f = 13), in which responsible decision-making (f = 8) plays a highly critical role in this dimension.

Table 4.
Code Co-occurrence Frequencies

Dimensions of Teacher Resilience	SEC Dimensions					Total
	Self-awareness	Self-management	Social awareness	Relationships skills	Responsible decision-making	
Personal Resources	3	8	4	1	4	20
Contextual Resources	2	5	4	2	2	15
Strategies	7	14	5	2	4	32
Outcomes	N/A	2	2	1	8	13
Total	12	29	15	6	18	80

4. Discussion

This study investigated critical incidents reported by four English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers regarding their resilience, as captured in narrative data. This approach to data collection and analysis also demonstrates that it enables researchers to understand better cause-and-effect relationships, complexities, the interconnectedness of resilience factors, and specificities (Carter, 1993; Scherff, 2008). Accordingly, regarding the first research question, the findings revealed that teachers experienced various types of challenges to resilience (e.g., collegial, student-related, and administrative), which aligns with those reported in other studies (e.g., Boldrini *et al.*, 2019; Gu & Day, 2013). Furthermore, the findings showed that challenges often occurred in complex ways, exemplified by the critical incidents of Amber and Cherry. That is to say, different types of challenges might be at work in a single critical incident related to teacher resilience, either sequentially or concurrently. The complex and intertwined nature of challenges in teacher resilience is also underlined in previous studies. Accordingly, such difficulties often result from the combination of different factors rather than a single one (Akçor & Ergül, 2025; Boldrini *et al.*, 2019; Gu & Day, 2013; Mansfield *et al.*, 2014).

Regarding the relationship between challenges and dimensions of teacher resilience, the findings revealed significant connections (e.g., between challenges and contextual resources and strategies). They highlighted the pivotal role of challenges in teachers' critical incidents (see Figure 5). Given that teachers constructed their critical incidents in a story form, paying attention to temporal sequentiality and causality, this finding is significant because it highlights that teachers tend to narrate their experiences of resilience, beginning with the challenges they faced. Therefore, it can be suggested that challenges catalyze teachers'

resilience processes, shaping how they use personal and contextual resources and strategies. As such, the initiating role of challenges is also underlined in the theoretical definitions of teacher resilience, in which resilience is associated with overcoming difficulties (Oswald *et al.*, 2003), recovering strengths despite challenges and impediments (Sammons *et al.*, 2007), and navigate through challenges (Beltman, 2012; Mansfield *et al.*, 2016).

Despite the critical role of challenges, teacher resilience is a multifaceted and dynamic process (Gu & Day, 2007) in which the interplay between personal resources, contextual resources, strategies, and outcomes shapes and reshapes the process (Beltman, 2020; Mansfield *et al.*, 2016). The findings of this study underpinned this notion and indicated commonalities and divergences compared to Mansfield *et al.*'s (2016) model (see Figure 5). This model emphasizes the bi-directional interaction between each dimension and underlines that "resources and strategies interact with each other in cycles over time, before resulting in adaptive outcomes" (Beltman, 2020, p. 214). The results of this study partially align with this model. In line with the model (see Figure 1), findings showed direct and indirect connections between dimensions at different levels. Despite strong connections between personal resources and strategies and contextual resources and strategies, moderate-level connections existed between personal resources and contextual resources, and weaker connections were found between outcomes and other dimensions, particularly between strategies and outcomes. Therefore, findings (see Figure 5) indicated that although personal and contextual resources interact with strategies, these interactions do not always produce the outcomes that Beltman (2020) and Mansfield *et al.* (2016) outline. Furthermore, the scarcity of contextual resources in Cherry's and Pearl's cases also showed that teachers may not always find or need contextual resources when encountering challenges. This can be explained by Akçor and Ergül's (2025) results, showing that social adaptation may pose challenges as teachers navigate complex relationships with students, colleagues, administrators, and parents while contending with hierarchical pressures, workplace mobbing, and oppressive attitudes. This finding is also critical because collaboration and cooperation with colleagues lead to distributed responsibilities, effective professional development, and better commitment.

The weaker connections between outcomes and other dimensions stemmed from two reasons. First, the analysis of critical incidents revealed failed strategies. That is to say, although teachers developed and employed specific strategies through their personal or contextual resources, some of these strategies proved ineffective, and they employed different strategies instead (see Figure 5). Secondly, findings also showed that strategies might appear as outcomes of resilience experiences (see Figure 5). Therefore, considering challenges, failed strategies, and strategies as outcome factors, teacher resilience is a dynamic process and multifaceted that often proceeds non-linearly, in which teachers employ different strategies based on challenges they face, personal and contextual resources they have to produce positive outcomes that contribute to their resilience capacity, personal resources, contextual resources, and strategies. This conceptualization primarily aligns with Beltman (2020) and Mansfield *et al.* (2016), incorporating refinements based on the findings of this study.

Regarding the second research question, findings indicated the critical role of the SEC in all dimensions of the teacher resilience process. Accordingly, self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationships skills, and responsible decision-making as SEC dimensions emerged as the primary or additional contributors in each dimension of the teacher resilience process. Strong connections between the SEC and strategies, as well as the SEC and personal resources, suggest that self-management plays a primary role, with contributions from social

awareness and responsible decision-making. The dominance of self-management in strategies in previous studies suggests that teachers effectively regulating their emotions can manage and overcome challenges (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009; Mansfield et al., 2012). The role of self-awareness and social awareness in the teacher resilience process also aligns with previous studies, underscoring that resilient teachers manage their emotions effectively, communicate clearly, and foster strong relationships (Mansfield et al., 2012, 2016). In addition, the connection between contextual resources and SEC appeared to be more moderate, yet with a more balanced distribution. Accordingly, this finding suggests that the SEC plays the mediator role between personal resources and contextual resources (Beltman et al., 2011; Jennings & Greenberg, 2009). Lastly, despite the weakest connection between SEC and outcomes, the predominance of responsible decision-making suggests that teachers may sometimes make decisions that others (e.g., colleagues, parents, students, etc.) are not content with; yet, such decisions fuel the sense of responsibility and satisfaction and contribute to their resilience (Baron & Baron, 2019; Najjarpour & Salim, 2024). These findings are critical in that they provide deeper insights into the SEC and its role in the teacher resilience process. Although SEC is often regarded as an important element of personal resources through which teachers may develop a capacity for resilience (Beltman, 2015; Mansfield et al., 2016), protective factors that contribute to teacher resilience (Ee & Chang, 2010) or manifestations of resilience (Knight, 2007), the interplay between SEC and factors in the teacher resilience process often remained in the background (Collie & Perry, 2019).

5. Conclusion

This study reports the analysis of critical incidents experienced by four experienced English teachers, focusing on the teacher resilience process and the role of SEC in this process. Findings revealed that teachers experienced various types of challenges that occurred in complex and interrelated ways. Besides, challenges play a pivotal role in the teacher resilience process, influencing and shaping the personal resources, contextual resources, and strategies that are used. Similarly, findings showed that the SEC also plays a critical role in the teacher resilience process, directly interacting with strategies, contextual resources, personal resources, and outcomes. However, it is worth noting that this study is limited to the self-reports of four teachers. Therefore, these findings cannot be generalized due to contextual and personal differences. However, the detailed picture of their critical incidents provides in-depth insights into the teacher resilience process and SEC, which may guide teachers with similar experiences and other researchers focusing on teacher resilience.

This study suggests several implications for pre-service and in-service teacher education, aligning with these findings. Schools are highly dynamic and fluid contexts where challenges and supportive elements coexist. Therefore, there is a need to integrate resilience training into both pre-service and in-service teacher education. These programs should instill in teacher candidates and teachers the necessary awareness, knowledge, and competence to cope with challenges skillfully, utilizing supportive elements. Hence, for pre-service teacher education programs, courses should incorporate role-plays, scenario-based activities, or real-life experiences of in-service teachers as both learners and teachers. Furthermore, seminars and workshops on resilience and SEC should be organized, particularly for in-service teachers, to prepare them for critical professional experiences. Other organizations and platforms where in-service teachers can share their experiences and strategies can also provide opportunities to establish support networks. Lastly, considering the limitations, further studies may focus on critical incidents collected from a larger sample to detect any

divergences and convergences identified in this study. Furthermore, given the complexity of the teacher resilience process, studies are needed to investigate the roles of other elements in this process by utilizing multiple sources of information, such as ethnographic field notes, observation, or simulated role-plays.

Ethical Issues

The study was conducted with the approval of the Ethics Committee of Karabük University (protocol code: E-78977401-050.04-409920, dated January 3, 2025).

Informed Consent Statement

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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